

Supplementary Material: Optimizing telework in an epidemic context: contrasting the infectious and non-communicable diseases perspectives

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25 **Supplementary Text 1: Calculation of the basic reproduction number R_0**

26 Our model of SARS-CoV-2 transmission among all employees of the company is summarised
 27 in the following set of ordinary differential equations:

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$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\lambda \cdot S$$

30
$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \lambda \cdot S - \sigma \cdot E$$

31
$$\frac{dP}{dt} = (1 - p_a) \cdot \sigma \cdot E - \rho \cdot P$$

32
$$\frac{dI_A}{dt} = p_a \cdot \sigma \cdot E - \gamma_A \cdot I_A$$

33
$$\frac{dI_S}{dt} = \rho \cdot P - \gamma_S \cdot I_S$$

34
$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \gamma_A \cdot I_A + \gamma_S \cdot I_S$$

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36 With numbers of susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection employees S , exposed but not yet
 37 infectious employees E , asymptomatic cases I_A , presymptomatic infectious cases P ,
 38 symptomatic infectious cases I_S , and recovered employees R . Although the total force of
 39 infection λ that the employees are exposed to SARS-CoV-2 includes the transmission risks
 40 both within and outside of the workplace, our calculation of R_0 only considers transmission in
 41 the workplace. Therefore, in this section we do not consider the force of infection in the
 42 community λ_C , nor the force of infection during teleworking λ_T .

43

44 We followed the next-generation matrix method outlined by Diekmann et al. (1990) to calculate
 45 the basic reproduction number of our model.

46

47 Let x_i the number of infected individuals in the i^{th} infected compartment among E , P , I_A , and I_S ,
 48 and x the vector $(x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3 \ x_4)$. The differential equations driving the numbers x_i may be written
 49 in matrixial form as:

50
$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f(X) - v(X)$$

51

52 Then the Jacobians of f and v may be computed, at the disease-free equilibrium where $S=N$
 53 and $E=P=I_A=I_S=R=0$, as:

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55
$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \beta & \beta \cdot v & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

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58
$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} -\sigma & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \sigma \cdot (1 - p_a) & -\rho & 0 & 0 \\ p_a \cdot \sigma & 0 & \gamma_A & 0 \\ 0 & \rho & 0 & -\gamma_S \end{pmatrix}$$

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60 The next-generation matrix K may then be computed as:

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$$K = -T \cdot \Sigma^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \beta & \beta \cdot v & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sigma} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\rho}(1-p_A) & \frac{1}{\rho} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{p_A}{\gamma_A} & 0 & \frac{1}{\gamma_A} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\gamma_S} \cdot (1-p_A) & \frac{1}{\gamma_S} & 0 & \frac{1}{\gamma_S} \end{pmatrix}$$

63

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \beta \cdot \frac{1}{\rho}(1-p_A) + \beta \cdot v \cdot \frac{p_A}{\gamma_A} & \beta \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma} & \beta \cdot v \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma_S} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

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$$\det(K - \lambda I) = -\lambda^3 \cdot \left(\beta \left[\frac{1-p_A}{\rho} + v \cdot \frac{p_A}{\gamma_A} \right] - \lambda \right)$$

67

68 The dominant eigenvalue of K is equal to R_0 .

69

$$R_0 = \beta \left[\frac{1-p_A}{\rho} + v \cdot \frac{p_A}{\gamma_A} \right]$$

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72 By re-arranging this equation, we obtain the transmission rate β as a function of R_0 :

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$$\beta = \frac{R_0 \cdot \rho \cdot \gamma_A}{[(1-p_A)\gamma_A + v \cdot p_A \cdot \rho]}$$

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76 **Supplementary Text 2: Calculation of the exposure-response functions**
77 **between teleworking and non-communicable disease risk**

78 Observed exposure-response functions

79 For all exposure-response functions, we calculated relative risk estimates for different
80 frequencies of teleworking, assuming that the baseline risk (i.e. a relative risk of 1) was
81 obtained at a teleworking frequency of 0 days per week. We assumed that there were 5
82 working days per week, hence 5 days of teleworking per week corresponded to a teleworking
83 frequency of 1.

84

85 For the U-shaped function, we used the estimates from (27) for depressive symptoms. The
86 baseline in this study for individuals with 0 days of teleworking was a self-reported score of
87 2.33. The other two estimates were for 1-4 days of teleworking (score of 1.71) and 5 days
88 (score of 2.08). We assumed that the estimate for “1-4 days” corresponded to 2.5 days per
89 week. We therefore had three relative risk data points to inform this function: 1 at 0 days per
90 week, 0.73 (1.71/2.33) at 2.5 days per week, and 0.89 (2.08/2.33) at 5 days per week.

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92 For the inverted U-shaped function, we used the estimates from (28) for lower back pain. The
93 baseline in this study for individuals with 0 days of teleworking was a self-reported pain in
94 49.9% of individuals. The other three estimates were for 1 day of teleworking (52.8%), 2-3
95 days (53.2%), and 4+ days (47.5%). We assumed that the estimate for “2-3 days”
96 corresponded to 2.5 days per week, and that the estimate for “4+ days” corresponded to 5
97 days per week. We therefore had four relative risk data points to inform this function: 1 at 0
98 days per week, 1.06 (52.8/49.9) at 1 day per week, 1.07 (53.2/47.5) at 2.5 days per week, and
99 0.95 (47.5/49.9) at 5 days per week.

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101 For the L-shaped function, we used the estimates from (20) for Edington risk. Since this study
102 reported adjusted beta regression coefficients calculated with logit links between outcomes
103 and variables, we converted these coefficients to probabilities using the formula

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$$105 \quad \text{probability} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\text{coefficient})}$$

106

107 The baseline in this study for individuals with 0 days of teleworking was an Edington risk in
108 3.5% of individuals (intercept beta coefficient = -3.33). The other three significant estimates
109 were for ≤8h of teleworking per month (2.0%, coeff = -3.9), 9-32h (1.3%, coeff = -4.3), and
110 ≥73h (1.0%, coeff = -4.6). We assumed that employees worked an average of 160h per month
111 (20 days of 8h each), hence that the estimate for “≤8h” corresponded to 0.25 days per week,
112 that the estimate for “9-32h” corresponded to 1 day per week, and that the estimate for “≥73h”
113 corresponded to 5 days per week. Note this corresponds to a conservative assumption where
114 we assume that, within each bracket, the lower risks are attained at the highest teleworking
115 frequencies. We therefore had four relative risk data points to inform this function: 1 at 0 days
116 per week, 0.57 (2.0/3.5) at 0.25 days per week, 0.38 (1.3/3.5) at 1 day per week, and 0.30
117 (1.0/3.5) at 5 days per week.

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119 The resulting relative risk functions are shown in Supplementary Figure 1.

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Supplementary Figure 1: Relative risk exposure-response functions with shapes and bounds derived from identified studies. Each point corresponds to an estimate, and lines are obtained by linear interpolation between the points. IU: inverted U-shaped; LS: L-shaped; US: U-shaped.

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131 **Supplementary Figure 2: Theoretical relative risk exposure-response functions.** Each
 132 point corresponds to an estimate, and lines are obtained by linear interpolation between the
 133 points. IU: inverted U-shaped; LD: linear decreasing; LI: linear increasing; LS: L-shaped; US:
 134 U-shaped. In these examples, the upper bounds of the IU and LI functions are set to 1.7, and
 135 the lower bounds of the LD, LS and US functions to 0.3, representing a change in relative risk
 136 of non-communicable disease due to teleworking of at most +/- 70% for all functions.

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Supplementary Figure 3: Cumulative incidence of non-communicable disease (NCD) at varying telework frequencies. Model simulations over 3 months using a telework frequency $\alpha = 0$ (no telework), 0.2 (1 day in 5), 0.4 (2 days), 0.6 (3 days), 0.8 (4 days) and 1 (full telework), for the relative risk for employees to eventually develop a NCD, in case of a L-shaped (LS, circles), U-shaped (US, triangles), inverted U-shaped (IU, squares), linear decreasing (LD, crosses) or linear increasing (LI, crossed squares) exposure-response relationship between telework and NCD risk. Baseline per-individual NCD incidence at a telework frequency of 0 is $8.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ days}^{-1}$.

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Supplementary Figure 4: Partial correlation coefficient between model parameters and disease outcomes. Parameter details and ranges explored are indicated in Table 1 in the main text. 400 parameter sets were sampled from Uniform distributions to calculate the coefficients. Points indicate mean estimates, and lines indicate 95% confidence intervals. ID: infectious disease; NCD: non-communicable disease.